

Supporting Information for Fully Automatable Relative Binding Free Energy Calculations with Enhanced Sampling using FAST/MBAR

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1 Derivation of the Bond Rescaling Jacobian

The elements of the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_{\vec{T}}(\vec{x})$ corresponding to a transformation \vec{T} are defined as follows:

$$J_{ij,\vec{T}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\partial T_i(\vec{x})}{\partial x_j} \quad (1)$$

A bond rescaling move between two atoms with coordinates \vec{r}_0 and \vec{r}_1 by a scaling factor s can be considered as a translation of \vec{r}_1 and all atoms bonded to it $\vec{r}_{movable}$ by $(s-1)(\vec{r}_1 - \vec{r}_0)$:

$$\vec{T}(\vec{r}_{movable}) = \vec{r}_{movable} + (s-1)(\vec{r}_1 - \vec{r}_0) \quad (2)$$

To calculate the determinant $|\mathbf{J}_{\vec{T}}(\vec{x})|$, we first note that $J_{ij,\vec{T}}(\vec{x}) = 0$ for all row elements $i \neq j$ corresponding to the stationary atoms, since their coordinates remain unchanged. Afterwards, we use the following well-known identity for the determinant of a block matrix $\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{D} \end{pmatrix}$:

$$|\mathbf{M}| = |\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{C}||\mathbf{D}| \quad (3)$$

If either \mathbf{B} or \mathbf{C} have only zero elements, the determinant reduces to:

$$|\mathbf{M}| = |\mathbf{A}||\mathbf{D}| \quad (4)$$

Therefore, all off-diagonal column elements corresponding to the stationary atoms do not contribute to the Jacobian determinant, even if they are not zero. This argument can be then iteratively applied to conclude that in our setting only the diagonal elements of each atom contribute to the determinant. For the transformation shown in Equation (2), all diagonal terms are unity except for the three coordinates corresponding to \vec{r}_1 , where each element is equal to s . Therefore, the Jacobian determinant for a bond rescaling transformation by a scaling factor s is:

$$|\mathbf{J}_{\vec{T}}(\vec{x})| = s^3 \quad (5)$$

This procedure can be straightforwardly generalised to multiple concurrent reversible

bond rescaling transformations with scaling factors s_1, \dots, s_N , in which case the Jacobian determinant is:

$$|\mathbf{J}_{\vec{T}}(\vec{x})| = \prod_{i=1}^N s_i^3 \quad (6)$$

2 Comparison to Available Experimental Data

Table 1: Comparison of calculated and available experimental $\Delta\Delta G^\ominus$ values. All values are in kcal/mol and reported as median (MAD).

Method	System				
	FXa	Thrombin	HSP90	PTP1B, uneq.	PTP1B, eq.
FAST w/o ES	-0.11 (0.15)	0.17 (0.44)	-0.10 (0.45)	-1.11 (0.31)	-1.07 (0.48)
FAST with ES	-0.17 (0.12)	0.12 (0.07)	0.22 (0.79)	-1.23 (0.46)	-1.30 (0.28)
AFE	-0.38 (0.01)	1.12 (0.06)	-0.21 (0.10)	-0.12 (0.21)	-2.73 (0.68)
Experimental	-1.01 ¹	—	1.19 ²	-0.87 ³	

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